

ADVANTAGES OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Kholmurodov Davron¹

Munira Xakimova²

¹student of University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences,
GavharStr1, Tashkent100149, Uzbekistan(dxolmurodov292@gmail.com.)

²scientific supervisor, senior teacher, University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences, Gavhar Str. 1, Tashkent 100149,
Uzbekistan(munirakhakimova2575@gmail.com)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13383524>

Abstract: This article explores the effectiveness, merits, and cons of digitalizing education. Furthermore, digital technologies have the potential to influence student performance and motivation. Some of their advantages include the potential educational value of digital technologies in foreign language teaching, recommendations on techniques for incorporating digital technologies into the educational process for work, and independent work organization of students and learners. Digital education creates new learning opportunities by engaging students in an interactive environment and utilizing hybrid tailored courses and creative learning methodologies.

Keywords: embodies, widespread, bibliographic, block chain, moos, podcast, charts, interactive, suitable, digital.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the world is developing dynamically. The 21st century made the humanity face a great challenge – COVID-19. Many business sectors, enterprises, as well as the education system at all levels had to switch to a distance format. However, it is worth mentioning that the higher school has managed to build a full-fledged online learning system based on the e-learning technologies, which open up unlimited opportunities for both teachers and students. The changes we observe touch upon the technologies, teaching methods and approaches to learning as well. The learning process is accompanied by a rapid increase of information flows, which need to be processed very quickly; otherwise the information becomes outdated and loses its relevance. But there is less time for receiving, processing and absorbing it. Due to the digitization of the society, there is a strong demand in application of new innovative and creative teaching tools that can contribute to the effective foreign language teaching. It has to be stated that the use of interactive tools and information and communication technologies in foreign language teaching allows students to be more involved in the learning process, hence these learning technologies are definitely promising, which determines the relevance of this research. They help to develop the intellectual and creative abilities of students, contribute to increasing the motivation of students in the educational process, and activate soft skills needed for successful candidates on the labor market. Improving the productive and receptive skills is one of the most important factors in acquiring language awareness in foreign language teaching. The development of communicative competence plays a fundamental role, since the latter embodies other types of competencies. So modern teachers strive to make learning process active through interactive teaching. Thus, the person being taught becomes creative and relates current information to past experiences to solve the problem or find an answer to a

question asked. The widespread use of games, the development of the Internet and the need to create attractive educational practices have led to the emergence of edutainment as a new form of education and professional training.[1]

2 DIGITAL APPLICATIONS

The most important soft skills nowadays for helping students develop their self-organization abilities are:

1) Easy Bib is a resource that may be used to write research papers in Russian as well as other foreign languages. It enables the creation of automatically generated bibliographic lists for scientific publications using Chicago/ Turban, MLA, APA citation.

2) Milk is a free tool that assists you in making calendars, creating an online schedule, and setting deadlines for tasks. It works with a number of platforms, including Android, iPhone, iPad, Twitter, and Gmail.3) Survey monkey is an online tool that educators and students can use to produce a variety of exams, surveys, and quizzes. It is convenient for completing different tasks with the help of content-language integrated learning and task-based learning technologies, as well as for getting feedback from teachers or other students. This resource is comparable to one called Class marker. 4) The next online tool for making so-called thought maps is Bubbl.us. These "memory cards" facilitate the arrangement of the information needed for the quickest possible study, memorization, and repetition. Both students and teachers use them at the start of the course to review and provide an engaging introduction to a new subject. 5) Create-a-Graph: Using this tool, you may create charts, tables, graphs, and other graphical representations of information. [2].

3 ADVANTAGES OF DIGITAL EDUCATION

The online learning system can be customized in a variety of ways thanks to its extensive range of features and resources. This is the most effective method for

developing a perfect learning environment that caters to every student's needs. [3]

a) Effectiveness. Online learning offers educators an effective way of delivering lessons to students. This way has a number of tools like videos, PDFs, podcasts, and teachers can use all of these tools as part of their lesson plans. The teacher can expand the lesson plan with online resources; as a result, teachers can become more educators that are effective.

b) Availability of time and place. Another benefit of online learning is the economic benefit. Online education is significantly more affordable compared to physical education. This is because online education does not require the cost of student transport, student meals, and most importantly, real estate. In addition, the entire course or teaching material is available online, eliminating the waste of paper, which is more affordable and beneficial to the environment.

c) Improving student attendance. With online classrooms, because classes are held at home or anywhere they choose, students will be less likely to miss classes

d) Suitable for a variety of learning styles Each student has a different learning path and individual learning style. Some students are visual learners, while some students prefer to learn through audio. Likewise, some students thrive in the classroom, while others are single students who are distracted by large groups.

People's ability to engage and communicate with one another may be declining as a result of all the new technologies, according to popular belief. Since many modern technologies are meant to be used independently, there are grave worries that kids may lose the social and cooperative skills they normally acquire in the classroom. The most expensive technology available today is cutting edge. It requires payment in order to use, which presents a challenge for the majority of public schools due to the net cost. Parents find it challenging as well because students become accustomed to electronics outside of the home! [4]

Introduction to the educational process of academic disciplines dedicated to block chain technology is one of the latest digital technology. One of the areas where block chains are actively integrated is the field of document storage and control. Here it is especially important to have guarantees that no one can manipulate the data and it will not be possible to overwrite it. Moreover, information about who added this or that record to the system is available to everyone. Blockchain is able to simplify the process of verifying education data, which is now used around the world. The only method of such verification can only be sending a request to an educational institution. The options for using the blockchain by the education system are not limited only to storing documents in a database.[5]

Information technology is actively used in all businesses in Japan, Singapore, the United States, Hong Kong, Estonia, and the United Kingdom. The Singapore

school system is regarded as one of the best and actively uses online learning. Blockchain-based educational platforms are currently widely utilized in Japan. In 2017, blockchain technology was formally implemented in schooling for the first time. The University of Nicosia made the decision to modernize in this way, making it easier to find and store any papers pertaining to the area of expertise (degrees, certificates, scientific publications, etc.). It was the first college to accept Bitcoin, a crypto currency, as payment for tuition. The university has launched MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses), which allow students from more than 83 countries to study remotely.[6]

4 Conclusions

In the modern world, education can be enhanced by the thoughtful use of technology. The benefits of distance learning are numerous. However, the relationship between the teacher and the student will always be crucial because it is through this interaction that learning occurs. Studying and analyzing the characteristics of digital translation—which we define as the process of translating texts from one language into another using specialized computer programs—is crucial. You need experts—software developers—to put all of the previously discussed concepts into practice. Blockchain technology is already booming, but there is a major barrier to its further development and application: a shortage of skilled and enthusiastic human resources.

Although it can be a very useful tool, technology is not meant to take the position of a teacher. The goal is to establish an adaptable, innovative learning environment. How technology is used to keep students engaged will determine how successful these efforts end up being. In the end, technology in education can open doors to new experiences, new discoveries, and innovative approaches to learning and collaboration.

REFERENCES:

- [1] S. Shelkovnikova, E. Krasnova, R. Avedova, 14th International Technology ,Education and Development Conference, 9354-9357 (2020).doi:10.21125/inted.2020.2592
- [2] M. Zacharova, Pedagogical and pshycological world 6, 47 (2020).
- [3] H. Kaur, International Journal of Applied Research <https://fedena.com/blog/2020/10/advantages-and-disadvantages-of-onlinelearning.html>
- [4] K. Courville, Technology and its use in Education: Present Roles and Future Prospects.
- [5] L. Lelu, Blockchain from A to Z. All about the technology of the decade (Eksmo,2018).
- [6] S. Raval, Blockchain technology in action (Piter, 2017).
- [7] E. Krasnova, E. Laskina, O. Moisoa, E. Velichko, SGEM 5, 3.4, 427-433 (2018).
- [8] D.Drescher, Fundamentals of blockchain: an introductory course for beginners in 25 Small Chapters